

VERRUCOUS CARCINOMA OF THE HAND

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ABSTRACT Skin verrucous carcinoma is a rare well-differentiated variant of squamous cell carcinoma that usually affects the feet but can touch any part of the body including the hands. We report the case of a large verrucous carcinoma on an old man's wrist with a second localization on the interdigital space that presented diagnostic problems and was successfully treated by surgical excision and secondary skin grafting.

KEYWORDS verrucous carcinoma, skin tumor, treatment

Introduction

Verrucous carcinoma is a rare, low-grade form of squamous cell carcinoma. It typically affects the oral cavity, larynx, genitalia, oesophagus, and rarely the skin. Skin verrucous carcinoma is a slow-growing, exophytic tumour with a broad base [1]. We present a patient with a large verrucous carcinoma on the hand.

Case report

A 78-year-old man presented with a large papillomatous mass on the wrist and a smaller one with similar aspect on 2nd interdigital space of the right hand. The history revealed that the symptoms began one year earlier after a minor trauma by a small nodule that was initially localized on the back of the right hand. This lesion had been surgically removed in a small dispensary with no histological proof. A month later similar lesions grew along the sides of the initial one resulting in a large multilobed exophytic painful tumour with purulent draining sinuses that goes all around the wrist with a similar smaller nodule on the dorsal face of the 2nd interdigital space and adjacent fingers of the same hand (Figure 1 and 2). During the examination, the tumour on the wrist was tender and renitent; it also discharged

fetid yellowish material as pressure was applied. The rest of the examination revealed no other abnormalities.

We first suspected an infectious origin because the draining sinuses and the purulent discharge of the lesion, but bacteriological and mycological tests were negative. Multiples biopsies were performed revealing tiny specific signs. There was an essential inflammatory reaction in the dermis with many plasmocytes. Pseudoepitheliomatous epidermal hyperplasia was also noted with cysts and sinuses in the epidermis and no cellular atypia (Figure 3)

After a radiological examination that confirmed that the lesion was restrained in the skin, the patient underwent surgical excision of the whole lesion with 10 mm margins as we couldn't confirm the benign or malignant nature of the lesion. No noble structure has been exposed during the surgery, and daily fatty dressings were done with a splint of the wrist in a neutral position to avoid any deformation or stiffness.

Histological examination of the excised tissues finally concluded to a verrucous carcinoma with clear resection margins. A semi-thick skin graft was then made. (Figure 4)

Control after surgery revealed good aesthetic results with no signs of relapse after one year of follow up. (Figure 5)

Discussion

The term "verrucous carcinoma" includes many nosological entities. It was first described by Ackerman in the oral cavity in 1948 [2]. It's also used to designate the commonly known Buschke–Loewenstein a tumour or giant condyloma acuminata in anourogenital locations [3]. The Carcinoma cuniculatum or

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Fig.1. Verrucous carcinoma of the right wrist and interdigital space

Fig.3. Histological image, H&E staining, pseudoepitheliomatous proliferation with multiple cysts in the epidermis, x 100

Fig.2. A circumferential tumour of the wrist with discharging crypts and sinuses

Fig.4. Result after skin graft

Fig.5. Result three months after surgery

verrucous carcinoma of the skin is more uncommon. It was described for the first time by Aird et al. in 1954 [4].

Clinically, it manifests as a wide, slowly growing papillomatous, cauliflower-like tumour with sometimes multiples crypts and sinuses, thus the designation “cuniculatum” which means rabbit burrow [5]. The feet are the most affected areas in about 90% of cases. However, any skin region can be involved [6]. In the present case, clinical aspect and evolution were typical for a verrucous skin carcinoma but unusual by its localization on the hand which has rarely been reported in the literature.

The etiopathology of these tumours involves many factors. The most well-identified causative agent is HPV infection, especially in the oral cavity, anogenital region, and the foot where the HPV is usually located. Other causative factors have been suggested such as chronic infections and scar tissues [8].

Histologically, the diagnosis can be difficult because of the misleading benign aspect of the tumour with very few cellular and nuclear atypia and low mitotic activity [9]. It's sometimes complicated to find the invasive proliferation that can be restrained in a small portion of the samples and multiples biopsies are occasionally necessary to confirm the diagnosis as it was the case with our patient.

Verrucous carcinomas are good prognostic tumours that rarely metastasise. Complete surgical excision is usually sufficient, but relapses are not rare. Some cases of anaplastic transformation have been described mostly after radiation therapy which is now considered contraindicated in the treatment of these tumours. Other treatment modalities were used such as chemotherapy, immunotherapy and local therapy with non-conclusive results. [7]

Conclusion

Verrucous carcinoma of the skin is a rare variant of squamous cell carcinoma with a better prognostic. The diagnosis of this kind of tumours is usually difficult since the histopathological aspect can sometimes be misleading with very few specific signs and that's

precisely what our case illustrates. It's therefore essential to insist on taking large and deep biopsies sometimes in multiples sites to avoid misdiagnosis.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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